

THE USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA TO ENHANCE STUDENTS' WRITING SKILLS IN ENGLISH

Khakimova Dilshoda Oybek qizi

dilshodaa.khakimova@mail.ru

Faculty of English philology and teaching, Uzbekistan State World Languages University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ANNOTATION: This article examines about the role and the use of social media in students' writing skills in English and discusses its advantages and some disadvantages as well. It can be seen from the paper is that students are more likely to express their opinions on social media and this encourages them to be open-minded and independent in their academic writing performance.

KEY WORDS: social sites, writing, blogs, online, learning, skills. methods, practice.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, proficiency in English writing has become an essential skill for communication in both personal and professional contexts. Social media platforms have emerged as powerful tools for language learners to improve their writing skills. The increasing popularity and use of social networks has affected all aspects of our lives. This research study aims to investigate the potential of students to use social media to develop their English writing skills.

Technology has affected almost every aspect of our lives and education is no exception. He revolutionized the traditional methods of teaching by introducing modern and innovative methodologies. With the continued popularity and growth of social media, many educators are considering using social media for educational purposes because they believe that social media has the ability to encourage active learning and collaboration among students. However, few teachers are concerned about the negative effects of social media on students' academic performance and

stop using it in education (Brabazon, 2007). Despite the popularity and inclusion of social media as a language teaching tool outside the classroom, research on the role of social media in the Pakistani context has focused on examining trends in its use among students, and there is a lack of empirical research examining its impact. using social networks in language learning. In this scenario, empirical studies should be conducted to investigate the effect of Facebook usage on students' writing skills.

II. METHODS

The development of the Internet and the emergence of network technology in communication has led to the use of social media worldwide. Facebook, Twitter, Skype are some social networking sites (SNS) that rely on social media technology. Social networks are used to communicate with peers, stay in touch with family and friends, get new information, advertise and promote products. Research by the National School Boards Association shows that Facebook membership has reached the 200 million mark worldwide, reflecting the success of social media in communication. Language production is an important component of the language acquisition process. Having students use social networking sites in a language that is not their own can help students learn the language.

Benefits of Social Media for English Writing Skills

Social media platforms offer a variety of benefits to language learners seeking to improve their writing skills. Firstly, social media provides a platform for learners to practice writing in a real-world context. Through social media, learners can interact with native speakers of English, exchange ideas, and express their opinions. This kind of interaction provides learners with an opportunity to practice writing in a way that is relevant and authentic. Secondly, social media platforms offer a wealth of resources for language learners. There are numerous online communities, groups, and forums where learners can engage with other learners and native speakers of English. These communities provide learners with access to a range of resources, including grammar guides, vocabulary lists, and writing prompts.

Thirdly, social media platforms enable learners to receive feedback on their writing from a diverse audience. By sharing their writing on social media, learners can receive comments and suggestions from other learners and native speakers. This feedback can help learners identify areas for improvement and develop their writing skills.

While social media platforms offer many benefits for language learners seeking to improve their writing skills, they also present some challenges. Firstly, social media can be a distraction for learners, particularly if they spend too much time scrolling through their feeds instead of practicing their writing skills. To avoid this, learners should set aside specific times for practicing their writing skills and limit their social media use during these times. Secondly, social media can expose learners to incorrect or informal language use. This can be particularly problematic for learners who are trying to develop their formal writing skills. To overcome this challenge, learners should seek out reliable sources of information and engage with native speakers who can provide feedback on their writing. Finally, social media can be overwhelming for learners who are just starting out. With so many resources and communities available, it can be difficult for learners to know where to begin. To overcome this challenge, learners should start by identifying their goals and focusing on specific areas of writing that they want to improve.

To make the most of social media for improving English writing skills, learners should follow some best practices. Firstly, learners should set specific goals for their writing practice and create a schedule for practicing their writing skills. This will help them stay focused and motivated. Secondly, learners should seek out reliable sources of information and engage with native speakers who can provide feedback on their writing. This will help them develop their formal writing skills and avoid common mistakes. Thirdly, learners should participate in online communities, groups, and forums where they can interact with other learners and native speakers of English. This will provide them with a supportive environment for practicing their

writing skills and receiving feedback. Finally, learners should use social media platforms as a supplement to traditional language learning methods, such as textbooks and classes. While social media can be a valuable tool for improving writing skills, it should not be the only method used.

III. RESULTS

The Output Hypothesis, developed by Swain (2007), considers "the act of language production (speaking or writing) as part of the second language learning process." Swain and Lapkin (1995) argue that the need to create language supports language learning. Therefore, encouraging and encouraging students to speak and experiment with language use is important to language learning. Long's (1996) interaction hypothesis posits that linguistic interaction resulting from face-to-face communication is important for language development. Based on the work of Vygotsky, Lantolf (2000) sociocultural approach to language acquisition emphasizes the role of interaction within the community of learners. Social networking sites can provide an opportunity for observational learning as students observe the behavior of others and can adapt their own language to communicate with others on social networks. Using social media for interactive purposes engages students in meaningful language tasks.

Research shows that technology-assisted instruction is more effective than traditional methods for helping students learn a language. Participation in social media such as Facebook and Twitter has been found to increase students' vocabulary and improve their writing skills (Lee, 2010; Yunus et al. 2012). However, Schmidt and Brown (2004) suggest that the use of social media should be considered as a combination of online and traditional classroom instruction.

The Facebook writing group also allowed students to connect with other peers and chat with friends without time constraints. Students reported that they read their friends' and peers' posts in the discussion forum and were encouraged to share their thoughts and opinions on the topic. A discussion forum allowed them to read and

comment on other students' posts. One of the students said that he read and re-read his text before putting it on the page, which helped him to self-correct his mistakes. Some students shared their experience that when they read the posts of their peers who wrote well in English, they paid more attention to their writing and any new words used by their peers in the discussion forum. they turned to the dictionary to find the meaning. This practice alone demonstrates the potential of students as gifted and motivated learners. When asked if they would like to continue this activity in the next semester, they were very willing to continue it because they saw it as a great opportunity to learn by interacting with their peers and teachers.

IV. DISCUSSION

Social networking sites (SNS) are now popular among the younger generation all over the world. Social networking sites are online platforms where people can create their profiles and interact with people around the world. Social networking sites provide an interactive platform that allows its users to form social relationships with other members to share information and knowledge related to real-life personal experience activities.

According to Asad et al (2012), people can share their thoughts, knowledge with each other, which helps them to increase their knowledge about the world and life. Social networking sites are gradually integrated into the way most people behave, think and interact with each other today, and that is why social networking sites have a lot of influence in the field of education and this influence affects students, o 'teachers, administrators and parents too.

People can discuss any topic or topic they like and they feel free to communicate or discuss on SNS rather than in a classroom environment. Sometimes students are not comfortable to communicate or discuss in a formal classroom, but they can freely discuss themselves on SNS, which increases their knowledge, and these sites have become very fashionable. , because more and more people are turning to SNS to share their daily events. not by meeting face to face but with online

friends. "SNSs provide platforms for students to learn and discuss outside of the formal classroom, so it encourages students to not only use the materials for academic purposes, but also encourages them to use them in everyday life. Using SNS and the student using SNS and using SNS found that there is a positive relationship between the academic performance of students who score high on the reading skills test and who have high grades. states that they can discuss the learning topic and acquire new information to help them improve their knowledge.He says that people learn new innovations in an interactive way, where there is more freedom of expression than in any formal learning environment. will be more.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, social media platforms offer a range of benefits to language learners seeking to improve their writing skills. By providing a platform for practicing writing in a real-world context, offering access to resources, and enabling learners to receive feedback from a diverse audience, social media can be a powerful tool for language learning. However, learners must also be aware of the challenges posed by social media, including distractions, exposure to incorrect language use, and overwhelm. With the advancement of technology, we need to update our language classes by integrating social media with traditional classroom practices to motivate and engage students in this growing digital world. The study found that learners' easy access to Facebook makes it a potential tool for use in language learning. Students were able to improve their writing skills because they were encouraged to write in an organized manner in the stress-free environment provided by Facebook. The use of Facebook increased student teacher interaction and allowed students to learn from their teachers and peers through collaborative learning experiences. However, Facebook should not be seen as a replacement or substitute for traditional classroom teaching, but rather as a tool to support language teaching in the classroom.

REFERENCE:

1. Abbasova, M. (2016). The impact of social networks on the students' English language in Azerbaijan.
2. Derakshan, A., & Hasanbassi, S. (2015). Social networks for language learning. *Theories and Practices in Language Studies*, 5(5), 1090-195.
3. Asad, S., Mamun, M. A., & Clement, C. K. (2012). The Effect of Social Networking Sites to the Lifestyles of Teachers and Students in Higher Educational Institutions.
4. Bani-Hani, N.A., Al-Sobh, M.A., & Abu-Melhim, A.H. (2014). Utilizing Facebook Groups in Teaching Writing: Jordanian EFL Students' Perceptions and Attitudes.
5. Bonk, C. J. (2009). *The World is Open, How Web Technology is Revolutionizing Education*. San Francisco, C.A.: Jossey-Bass.
6. Choi, W-C. (2008). The Role of Online Collaboration in Promoting ESL Writing. *English Language Teaching*, 1(1), 34-49. Retrieved 14 July 2017, from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v1n1p34>